

Available Bandwidth Guided On-Demand Distance Vector Protocol for FANETs

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Abstract—Video streaming in unmanned aerial vehicles helped in performing surveillance, inspection, and map generation tasks. However, packet loss in multi-drone networks frequently occurs due to the high mobility of the nodes and to congestion. In this article Available Bandwidth Guided On-Demand Distance Vector (ABODV) protocol for Flying Ad Hoc Networks (FANETs) is introduced, which has some enhancement over the traditional Ad-hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV) protocol. In this protocol, the source node chooses the neighbors who has highest number of entries in their routing table, leading to reduction in the overhead. ABODV was implemented and tested using a special simulator environment. It was noticed that the adopted strategy of reducing the neighboring nodes in some cases had led to congestion. Therefore, to overcome congestion, the available bandwidth parameter was included for optimizing FANETs performance. This resulted in distributing the load in a balanced way. Existing available bandwidth estimation methods were investigated in terms of precision and speed. A FindPath tool for estimating the available bandwidth has been suggested, implemented, and evaluated. The customized protocol seemed to give satisfactory results for applications using FANETs.

I. INTRODUCTION

In unmanned aerial vehicle networks, the nodes normally have limited transmission ranges, and some nodes cannot communicate directly with each other. Hence, routing paths in FANETs potentially contain multiple hops, and every node has the responsibility to act as a router. Because of the importance of routing protocols in dynamic multi-hop FANETs, a lot of routing protocols have been proposed in the last decade. There are some challenges that make the design of a mobile ad hoc network routing protocol a tough task. These challenges are represented for example in the scalability issue. Having a large number of nodes in FANETs, and the issue of scalability make the design of a FANETs routing protocol a tough task. Asking for a route by a FANET node is considered an overhead because all neighbors have to search for the desired route, especially when a large number of neighbors exists [2], [12]. AODV protocol stores the next-hop routing information for destination nodes, reducing the number of broadcast messages by discovering routes on-demand instead of keeping complete up-to-date route information. A timer is countdown to determine the usability period of routing table. If a route is not requested within that period, it expires, and a new route has to be found when needed. Each time a route is used, its lifetime is updated. There are four types of unicast messages in AODV: Route Request (RREQ) for route discovery initiation, Route Reply (RREP) for route discovery completion, Route Error (RERR) for link breakage indication, Route Reply

Acknowledgement (RREP-Ack) for unidirectional link invalidation. The sequence numbers are the key idea for removing the old and invaluable information from the network, and they act as timestamps to prevent this distance vector protocol from the loop problem. The destination sequence number for each possible destination node is stored in the routing table, and it is updated in the routing table when the node receives a message with a greater sequence number. The node can change the destination sequence number in the routing table if it is offering a new route to itself or if some route expires or simply breaks [2].

When a node joins the network, it broadcasts itself with a sequence number equal to zero. The other nodes in the network add an entry for it with the same sequence number zero, and the sequence number is incremented by 2 when broadcasting the new updates, but it is incremented by 1 when a node detects a broken link to a node. The node also keeps its own sequence number, which must be incremented only in two cases: before it sends RREQ message, and when the node sends a RREP message, responding to the RREQ message. In the second case the sequence number must be incremented to the maximum of the current sequence number and the sequence number in the received RREQ message. The sequence numbers must be treated as unsigned integers so that the possible rollovers can occur. AODV protocol supports the sequence numbers to be rolled over without any problem.

For monitoring such large and mobile networks, available bandwidth estimation is an essential tool, which provide us with information about the current usage of network resources. It can also be used to monitor and verify the quality of service QoS with accurate information to manage the agreements between the nodes [3], [15]. Capacity is the maximum rate at which packets can be transmitted by a node, and available bandwidth is the link's unused capacity. As available bandwidth has a significant impact on the performance of many applications that run over FANETs, tools for measuring it in terms of reliability, accuracy and speed has to be created [1], [14]. Pathload, PathChirp, Spruce, and Diet-TOPP are examples of such a tool.

In FANETs, one of the essential concerns is to improve the QoS by moving the data between the nodes without loss or delay. Available bandwidth measuring tools rely on one of two principles: either sending fixed size packets with variable intervals, or sending variable size packets with fixed time intervals. It is noticed that the tools using a probing train gives

an accuracy better than those using a pair of probing packets but it requires a longer probing time [11]. Providing a reliable tool for estimating the available bandwidth with good accuracy and speed is still required.

The *problem can be stated* as follows, packet loss in multi-drone networks frequently occurs due to the high mobility of the nodes and to congestion. As a *contribution*, an on-demand distance vector protocol was adopted where neighbor nodes that has highest number of entries in their routing table were chosen, leading to reduction in the overhead, however congestion might happen. Therefore, available bandwidth estimation was included to guide the routing and to overcome congestion and distribute the load in a balanced way.

II. RELATED WORKS

The available bandwidth estimation approaches applied in FANETs are: 1) *Measurement-based* (probe rate models PRM and probe gap models PGM [16].) PRM use trains of probe packets at increasing rates for estimating the available bandwidth. PGM base the estimation on the dispersion gap between two consecutive probing packets. These approaches add high traffic overhead. 2) *Analytical* (such as a Markov model, effective link model, or using Kalman filters [17].) These approaches are highly topology-dependent and in a distributed and mobile scenario with a random topology, obtaining and maintaining the information required by an analytical model is extremely difficult. 3) *Calculation-based* that measures local information about the used bandwidth by broadcasting HELLO message packets that are used for discovering local topology in routing protocols [18]. If the exchanges are not too frequent, this technique is considered non-intrusive.

Other approaches use MAC layer information to estimate available bandwidth and delay information [19] in discrete time intervals by averaging the throughputs of the recent packets. This estimation is not accurate because of the frequent change in the channel condition. Distributed estimation of the available bandwidth with channel monitoring method, collision estimation and back-off duration prediction is used [20], while, the channel monitoring cannot reflect the future status of the link. A scheme for estimating available bandwidth in FANETs based upon collision probability, idle period synchronization and random waiting time was proposed [21], where the collision probability at each node is estimated using distributed Lagrange interpolation polynomial before the actual transmission of data. Calculating the available bandwidth is frequently made by estimating the minimum residual bandwidth among the intermediate nodes throughout the route [22], which is inaccurate since measuring the utilization of the medium locally ignores the self-interference of a flow at consecutive links and the simultaneous idle times of neighbor links.

Providing efficient data forwarding protocols in FANETs, ensuring link availability and network stability have been studied [23].

Optimizing routes to achieve the ergodic rate density (ERD) in each link has been proven, and some sub-optimal and more realistic protocols have been presented [24]. Geographic based routing protocols were proposed such as parallel routing protocol (PRP), where multiple data packets over disjoint paths can be routed simultaneously, where each node in the network can maintain updated information about its own location in the virtual grid of the network using GPS that is not always available for such nodes in reality [27]. Several routing protocols were analyzed and their performance was compared for networks that are used for video streaming [28]. Video streaming is possible for such networks using the traditional routing protocols with acceptable quality, while the performance varies depending on the network scenario and the used video traffic. A stochastic geometry approach was proposed to characterize the one-way and two-way communication characteristics, especially the signal to interference ratio (SIR), and interference to noise ratio (INR) distributions of mmWave ad-hoc networks using directional antennas, random blockage models, and ALOHA channel access [26]. Utilizing mmWave in FANETs, an optimal geographic routing protocol (OGRP) and a directional Medium Access Control (MAC) protocol with small range and using directional antennas were proposed [25], without analyzing or comparing the performance of the suggested protocols with others that work in Wi-Fi networks. While, the effect of using mmWave on the performance of FANETs was not studied.

III. AVAILABLE BANDWIDTH GUIDED ON-DEMAND DISTANCE VECTOR PROTOCOL (ABODV)

Before sending a RREQ message, the source node sets the hop count to zero, and saves the RREQ ID and its own address to a buffer for a specified amount of time, so that it recognizes the replies. When a node receives the RREQ message, it checks the period between the last RREQ messages from the same node and discards the message if it is under a certain limit. Then the node increases the hop count by one in the RREQ message and updates it in its routing table based on the sequence number and the requested node's address. The node marks that the route is valid to the requested node and adds information about the next hop specifying to which node the message should be forwarded [5], [13].

The source node needs to count the lifetime of the route to the requested node. If the sequence number in the routing table is greater than in the received message, the node should not modify the sequence number in the routing table. However, only if the D field is not set, the node can generate the route reply message (RREP) if the destination is the node itself or if it has a valid route and has the same or greater destination sequence number.

When the node generates the RREP message, it copies the destination address and the requested node's sequence number to the corresponding RREP message's fields. If the receiver is

the destination node then its own sequence number is incremented and copied to the destination's sequence-number field.

The hop count is set to zero and the lifetime field of the RREP message is set to the initial timeout value of the node. If the receiver is an intermediate node, then it just copies destination sequence number from the routing table and adds the node address from where it has received RREQ message to the destination address field [9]. The node must add the hop count with the lifetime from the routing table to the RREP. The lifetime T_L is calculated by subtracting the current time T_{curr} and the expiration time T_{expir} from the routing table:

$$T_L = T_{curr} - T_{expir}$$

When the RREP message is created it is sent using unicast to the next hop in order to be delivered to the requested node. The hop count is incremented along the path, so at the end, it corresponds to the actual distance between the nodes. When a link breakage happens, the node must invalidate the existing route in the routing table entry as shown in Fig. 1. The node must list the affected destinations and determine which neighbors can be affected with this breakage. Eventually, the node must send the route error (RERR) message to the corresponding neighbors [6].

Fig. 1. Link breakage

If the node detects a link breakage in the active route, it makes a list of unreachable destinations. The destination sequence numbers for the entries in the routing table for the unreachable destinations must be incremented. After this, the entry for the unreachable nodes must be set to invalid lifetime, where *lifetime* T_L is set to the *current time* T_{curr} plus specific *deletion time* T_{del} :

$$T_L = T_{curr} + T_{del}$$

So that, the entry is not deleted from the routing table before the lifetime expires. Then the RERR message with the unreachable destinations should be unicasted for one neighbor or broadcasted to the neighbors with TTL value set to 1. The DestCount field in the RERR message describes the number of the unreachable node addresses [10]. AODV uses the Hello messages periodically to inform its neighbors that the link to the node is alive. The Hello messages are broadcasted with

TTL equals to 1, so that the message will not be forwarded further. When node receives the Hello message, it will update the lifetime of the node information in the routing table. If the node does not get information from its neighbors for a specified amount of time, then the routing information in the routing table is marked as lost. The precursor list contains the information about which nodes can possibly forward the messages to this route. Precursor list contains the information to which neighbor the errors should be forwarded when the possible break occurs [7]. AODV protocol does not need any central administrative system to handle the routing process. Reactive protocols like AODV tend to reduce the control traffic messages overhead at the cost of increased latency in finding new routes.

The route discovery process in reactive routing protocols is considered an overhead, especially when it is initiated more frequently due to the node mobility. Therefore, a customized ad-hoc protocol, called Available Bandwidth Guided On-Demand Distance Vector (ABODV) is suggested. ABODV protocol does not need any central administrative system to handle the routing process, and it is designed for networks with tens of mobile nodes. ABODV suggests an enhancement over AODV protocol to minimize the busyness of nodes in a network when a route discovery process is initiated. This is achieved by minimizing the amount of nodes that are responsible to do the route discovery process. Therefore, when a source node wants to communicate with a destination node it broadcasts its request to its directly connected neighbors to get an offer from them with a low cost route. When a node asks its neighbors about a route to a desired destination one of the following possibilities should occur:

- If one of the directly connected neighbors are the destination, the source node can share information with it directly.
- Else, if the neighbors have a route to the desired destination they reply to the source with a RREP message, which contains information about the destination with a minimum cost.
- Else, when the neighbors do not have any entry to help the source with a route to the desired destination, all of them start a normal route discovery procedure until they offer a route to the destination.

For example, when source node S wants to communicate with destination node D, it starts a route discovery procedure. By asking the neighbors about a possible route to node D with a RREQ message. However, instead of making all of them start a route discovery process, which is an overhead in wireless ad-hoc networks, it chooses a group of them as follow: The source node S asks its neighbors first about the number of entries in their routing tables before sending the RREQ messages as shown in Fig. 2a. Then each node reply with a packet, which contains its ID and the number of entries N in its routing table as shown in Fig. 2b. Then node S chooses from its neighbors the nodes with maximum number of entries as in Fig.2c. Thus, it chooses 50% of them. Those active nodes have advantages over other directly connected nodes because they have too many relations and the probability of finding the desired route through them is higher.

Choosing only the nodes with the maximum number of entries leads to congestion as frequently decisions have to be made in them, and loops may occur. To minimize this overhead we decrease the percentage from 50% to 25% of directly connected nodes, which have maximum number of entries. The remaining 25% of directly connected nodes are those with the minimum number of entries, so a noticeable balance is achieved. Then each node who received the RREQ do the same procedure as in Fig. 2d, until they reach the destination. Optimization of the available bandwidth is also performed to overcome the congestion that might occur.

Fig. 2. ABODV selective route discovery process

The source node who sent the RREQ message is not included inside the elected nodes, like when C does not take S

into account and it chooses G or H, and E does not take S into account it sends only to C and F. Node S chooses node C (4 entries) and node E (3 entries) in its group. It may also choose node B (3 entries) instead of E because both have the same number of entries. If the chosen group starting the route request does not offer the desired route, or does not reach the destination, the source node starts another route discovery process, choosing all neighbors like pure AODV, and if those also do not reach the destination, then the source node knows that it cannot reach the destination. It is proved that choosing 3 neighbors offers good enhancement for networks with large number of nodes.

In ABODV protocol when a source node A wants to communicate with a destination node M, the source node does not broadcast its RREQ to its all neighbors but it chooses a group of them according to the number of entries contained in the routing table so RREQ isn't flooded in whole network. As a result, we minimize nodes involved in route discovery process. Fig. 3 shows some measurements taken from the ABODV simulator.

Fig. 3. ABODV protocol performance

A simulator was implemented to evaluate the performance of the ABODV protocol. We notice that ABODV does not affect all network nodes in route discovery process, and this is a required feature for ad hoc protocols especially when having a large number of nodes in an active network and minimizes the overhead.

IV. AVAILABLE BANDWIDTH ESTIMATION

All the tools used for available bandwidth estimation so far rely on one of two principles, either using fixed size packets with variable time interval, or variable size packets with fixed time interval [8]:

- *Variable size packets:* A single probing train consists of N packets differ in size in a linear manner as shown in Fig. 4, i. e. if the packet i has size P_i , the size of $i + 1$ packet is $P_{i+1} = P_i + \Delta P$. The size of first sent packet is P_1 .

Fig. 4. Probing train of N packets

With varying packets size and time interval, the linear increase in the size of packets, enables the receiver to determine which packets have been received and which one was lost on the way [4]. Therefore, the receiver can locate any packet in the probing train when knowing the size of that packet. The relationship between the packets *order* and *size* within the probing train of 30 packets is almost incrementally linearly proportional, taking a packet size difference of $\Delta P = 50$ bytes.

– *Variable time interval*: Here the time interval between the probing train packets is also not fixed, but decreases linearly. In other words, if the time interval at packet i is T_i , and this interval at the following packet $i + 1$ is $T_{i+1} = T_i - \Delta T$ according to the following:

$$T_1 > T_2 > T_3 \dots > T_{N-2} > T_{N-1} \quad (1)$$

The relationship of time interval between probing packets and the order of these packets is decreasingly ascendingly proportional, taking a time interval $\Delta T = 0,5$ ms.

The receiver should have a prior knowledge about the time intervals between the probing train packets when they were sent, and should register arrival time of each packet. The receiver can locate any received packet through its size, so the duty of the receiver is to compare time intervals between probing packets when sending them (already available), and when received. While sending the probing packets at a rate equal or less than the available bandwidth value $R_{send} \leq AB_w$, the time intervals between consecutive received probing packets are equal to those between consecutive sent probing packets. If we neglect the delay experienced by probing packets while passing through the network (delay suffered by all packets and it is the time they need to cross the network path), i. e.:

$$T_{1,snd} = T_{1,rcv}; T_{2,snd} = T_{2,rcv}; \dots; T_{N-1,snd} = T_{N-1,rcv} \quad (2)$$

When the probing packets *transmission rate* exceeds available bandwidth, the relationship (2) becomes not correct and the probing packets have to stand in the waiting queue, leading to an increase in time intervals between the consecutive probing packets when received. Based on the above, the receiver determines the available bandwidth at the packet, among consecutive probing packets, where the time interval starts to increase in comparison with what it had from previous values. The above can be summarized by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{i,snd} &= T_{i,rcv}; R_i \leq AB_w \\ T_{i,snd} &< T_{i,rcv}; R_i > AB_w \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

We can calculate the instantaneous transmission rate at packet i as follows:

$$R_i = \frac{P_i}{T_i}$$

While the instantaneous probing rate of the next packet is:

$$R_{i+1} = \frac{P_{i+1}}{T_{i+1}} = \frac{P_i + \Delta P}{T_i - \Delta T}$$

At package i the instantaneous probing rate, relative to primitive values, is as follows:

$$R_i = \frac{P_1 + (i-1)\Delta P}{T_1 - (i-1)\Delta T} \quad (4)$$

We note that the instantaneous probing rate is a function of packet order in the probing train. Where the values of each of the following parameters: P_1 , T_1 , ΔP and ΔT are known and specified in advance. Fig. 5 shows the change in the probing rate.

From the above it is clear that the instantaneous probing rate changes with time within what we call the possible or *available probing range*.

Fig. 5. Relationship between instantaneous probing rate and probing packets order, $N = 30$ packets, $\Delta T = 0.5$ ms, $\Delta P = 50$ bytes

Available probing range is defined by two limit values: the lower probing rate R_{min} , and the higher probing rate R_{max} , which can be calculated by the following equations:

$$R_i = \frac{P_1}{T_1}; R_{max} = \frac{P_N}{T_N} = \frac{P_1 + (N-1)\Delta P}{T_1 - (N-1)\Delta T} \quad (5)$$

where N is the number of packets forming the probing train. The length of the probing train is calculated by combining the time intervals between all the packets as follows:

$$T_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^N T_i = T_1 + (T_1 - \Delta T) + (T_1 - 2\Delta T) + (T_1 - (N-1)\Delta T) \quad (6)$$

Combining accuracy and speed in the estimation process is an essential requirement for approving the tool. For this, we tried to look for a method that can combine between both requirements accuracy and speed, with the fulfillment of the following constraints:

a. *Excluding synchronization*: between sender and receiver, that is, all the information needed by the receiver can be found in received probing packets, without the need to reconnect with the sender.

b. *Eliminating repetition*: since it has a bad effect on the estimation-process continuation time, and the tool should have an acceptable transparency for the network.

c. *Accuracy of estimation*: accuracy is relative, and we think that accuracy of the tool should be high at low available bandwidth values rather than at high values (problems of packets delay and loss increase when available bandwidth is small).

A measurement tool called *FindPath* is used which gives importance for low values of available bandwidth, which distinguishes it in comparison with other tools. The design of this tool relies on the combination of the two principles mentioned above, in which both of probing packets size and time intervals between these packets are changed. The tool uses a single probing train (i.e., repetition canceling), whose length is defined based on the desired precision. The *FindPath* tool using UDP protocol sends a single probing train consisting of N packets differ in their size from each other linearly, and time intervals between the probing train packets is not constant but decreases linearly as well. All what we have to do is determining the appropriate values of R_{min} and R_{max} for the required estimation process. Initially, identifying the values of R_{min} and R_{max} formed a challenge and was time consuming.

FindPath can estimate the available bandwidth within $[0, 8]$ Mbps, with the focus on low values of the available bandwidth. As we mentioned the size of packets in a probing train built by *FindPath*, increases in a linear way. The largest packet size is 1500 Bytes (taking into account UDP protocol overhead added to the original packet size), while the smallest packet size being sent is determined based on the number of sent packets N , and the amount of size change ΔP . Number of packets used in the probing train, determines the number of levels of available bandwidth which can be estimated, and so this determines the level of required precision. If the number of packets is $N = 30$ packets (additional packet is sent after a specified time interval when sending probe packets stops. In order to obtain the last value which can be estimated), and packet size difference between two consequent packets is $\Delta P = 50$ bytes, the values of packets sizes which form the probing train are the following: 50, 100, 150, ..., 1500 bytes, i. e. $P_1 = 50$ bytes.

In order to determine the time interval between successive packets, as we said earlier, the time interval between the probing packets decreases linearly with the successive sending of packets. The time interval of the first packet is $T_1 = 16$ ms and the time interval of the last packet is $T_{N-1} = 1.5$ ms. The number of packets is $N = 30$. The amount of decrease in time is $\Delta T = 0.5$ ms. From all what preceded and basing on equations (1, 2, 3, 4), we get the following parameters: $P_1 = 50$ bytes, $T_1 = 16$ ms, $\Delta P = 50$ bytes, $\Delta T = 0.5$ ms. Substituting in equation (5) we calculate the minimum and maximum transmission rates:

$$R_{min} = \frac{P_1}{T_1} = \frac{50.8}{16 \text{ ms}} = 25 \text{ Kbps}$$

$$R_{max} = \frac{P_N}{T_{N-1}} = \frac{1500.8}{1.5 \text{ ms}} = 8 \text{ Mbps}$$

Substituting in equation (6) we get $T_{total} = 262.5$ ms.

To carry out the task of available bandwidth estimation, we designed an experimental network within a controllable environment using six COEX Clover drones as shown in Fig. 6,

where four UAVs were used in order to generate, send and receive each of the cross-traffic and probing packets, as well as two routing nodes. One of the conducted experiments adopted the following scenario: the transmitters were hovering at a height of 23 meters, and the receiving nodes at 8 meters, while the relay nodes at a height of 13 meters and 18 meters, respectively.

Fig. 6. Test network composed of six COEX Clover drones, cross-traffic sender and receiver, probing-packets sender and receiver, and two routing nodes

In the process of estimation, we measure the available bandwidth for the link with a capacity of 10 Mbps, located between the two relay UAVs. The *cross-traffic* generator generates cross-traffic packets at a steady rate. Estimation process is repeated several times. The objective of repetition is to get accurate values by calculating the average of the values that have been achieved.

Fig. 7 shows the relationship between the available bandwidth and cross-traffic for *FindPath*. Fig. 8 shows the relationship between the relative error and the available bandwidth for *FindPath*.

Fig. 7. Available bandwidth estimation results

Values of cross-traffic that have been adopted are: 2 Mbps, 3 Mbps, 4 Mbps, 5 Mbps, 6 Mbps, 7 Mbps, 8 Mbps, 8.5 Mbps,

9 Mbps, 9.5 Mbps. It was noticed that FindPath gives acceptable accuracy at low values of available bandwidth. We can increase the accuracy or change the range of measurement by increasing the number of sent packets and by changing the time interval between those packets.

Fig. 8. Relationship between available bandwidth and relative error for FindPath

Video streaming in multi-drone networks requires high bandwidth and frequently suffers from packet loss due to the high mobility of the nodes and to congestion. To overcome congestion and distribute the load in a balanced way, the FindPath tool was used for estimating the available bandwidth.

V. OVERHEAD REDUCTION

Sensor nodes send their data to the base station using paths that have minimum number of relay nodes, i.e., the number of hops traversed by the packets are kept to minimum. Available bandwidth values on the links are used as weights on a graph and the best path is chosen with respect to these dynamically changing weights. Link is not used if alternate lower loaded paths are available. The algorithm starts where there is only one stage to reach destination, finds optimal solution, then gradually finds current optimal solution from preceding one, until the whole task is solved without checking the calculated optimal paths in every iteration. This results in reduction in calculations. S is a source node, and D is a destination node (refer to Fig. 1). Decision variables x_n are immediate destination on stage n, if $n=4$, the selected route is $S \rightarrow x_1 \rightarrow x_2 \rightarrow x_3 \rightarrow x_4 = D$, where $f_n(s_t, x_n)$ is total cost of best overall policy for remaining stages, state s_t , stage n , and selects x_n as immediate destination. x_n^* value of x_n that minimizes $f_n(s_t, x_n)$, $f_n^*(s_t)$ minimum value of $f_n(s_t, x_n)$,

$$f_n^*(x_n) = \min_x f_n(s_t, x_n) = f_n(s_t, x_n^*)$$

$$f_n(s_t, x_n) = c_{ij} + f_{n+1}^*(x_n)$$

where c_{ij} is the immediate cost (stage n) and $f_{n+1}^*(x_n)$ is the minimum future cost (stages $n+1$), i is the current state s_t and j is the immediate destination x_n . Destination (state D) is reached at the end of stage 4, $f_5^*(D) = 0$.

The objective is to find $f_1^*(S)$ and corresponding route by successively finding $f_4^*(s_t)$, $f_3^*(s_t)$, $f_2^*(s_t)$, for each possible states s_t , and then using $f_2^*(s_t)$ to solve for $f_1^*(S)$.

To determine the routes for nodes in FANETs efficiently, scalable and distributed routing scheme can be applied.

Possible paths between ingress/egress node pairs and the amount of bandwidth available on each of them should be known, regardless of the underlying topology. Each path is annotated by the allocated bandwidth. The number of hops can be used to guide the selection of one path if multiple suitable paths exist. *Bandwidth metric* is used along with the *number of hops*. The amount of available bandwidth along each path between the nodes changes dynamically. To handle such dynamic situations, each node maintains the amount of *available bandwidth* on all the paths to other nodes, and a list of *logical paths* to other nodes. A logical path between the pair of nodes consists of a sequence of nodes. To limit the amount of information to be maintained, some lengthy paths should be eliminated. The *end-to-end delay* may become too long and the service becomes unsatisfactory even though the available bandwidth meets the basic request. A pre-define path length L_r should be defined. If the path length between two nodes L_i is higher than L_r , then this logical path is eliminated.

The source node forwards *probes* along all the existing paths to the destination node. If multiple suitable paths are available, then one can be selected either randomly, or based on other criteria such as the number of physical hops along the path, or the actual bottleneck capacity of the path. To choose the possible paths, a *delay threshold* d_{th} is used. For a possible logical path, the number of logical hops H should not exceed the specified delay threshold. In this manner, the overhead incurred in forwarding the probe on paths that may not satisfy the requirements is reduced. If no path between the chosen ingress/egress node pair has sufficient bandwidth to satisfy the requirement, the probe is *pruned* and not forwarded further. Otherwise, it is forwarded to the next node along the selected path. This continues until the probe reaches the destination node. Logical paths from source node to destination node may share a common portion at the beginning. *The probe is forwarded only once along the shared path*, a technique called *probe aggregation*, which aids in the reduction of the overhead associated with forwarding the probes. The constraints of the flow are expressed in terms of the required bandwidth B_w . The bandwidth of the path is compared with B_w , and if this bandwidth is higher than B_w , the probe is forwarded to next node. This process of forwarding the probe is repeated. If the bandwidth of the entire path is greater than B_w the probe is forwarded to next node. If the paths share a common egress node, a single probe is forwarded to this node. The probe is pruned when the bandwidth of the paths between *certain nodes* is not sufficient. The number of probe messages has an upper bound of U_p .

The control message overhead of the routing scheme increases slowly with the delay threshold d_{th} than that of the traditional routing scheme. The probe overhead can be reduced by employing *probe aggregation* and *probe pruning* techniques. We use the delay threshold d_{th} to compute the logical paths: a logical path from a source proxy to a destination proxy should be no more than d_{th} logical hops longer than the shortest logical path between them. Fig. 9 illustrates the amount of overhead relative to the delay threshold measured by logical hops. The *overhead*, which is the total number of logical hops that probes traverse, is used as a performance metric to evaluate the scalability. The lower the

overhead, the less the consumed bandwidth, and hence the more efficient the scheme. Routing effectively reduces the control overhead by sending only one probe between every involved ingress/egress pair. As shown in Fig. 9 the overhead of ABODV routing grows less than traditional routing, e.g., when $d_{th} = 4$ the overhead decreases to around 98% in the case of pruning, and to 78% in the case of probe aggregation. The scalability of routing via probe flooding can be improved by precomputing only the optimal paths.

Fig. 9. Probe aggregation and probe pruning

VI. CONCLUSION

The characteristics of ad hoc networks and their routing protocols were investigated. Possible metrics to measure the performance of FANETs routing protocols were studied. ABODV protocol was introduced and its core architecture was described. The basic actions related to the route discovery process were studied. A special simulator showed that ABODV protocol will perform better in the networks with dynamic traffic, and it's more scalable than AODV. This enhancement can be added to any reactive routing protocol. Moreover, we found that FindPath gives good accuracy at low values of available bandwidth, better than at high values of available bandwidth, in comparison with other existing tools for available bandwidth estimation. Therefore, if the nodes in a FANET have low available bandwidth, we can use FindPath to optimally determinate the value of available bandwidth that we have to use for sending our data, which offers us the ability to overcome congestion and to achieve load balance over the network paths.

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